

Practice Abstract no. 36

Industry & food system actors' views on bottlenecks preventing data sharing

The #Data4Food Cluster comprising the [DRG4Food](#), [FOODITY](#), [FoodDataQuest](#), and [SOSFood](#) projects organised a joint workshop in June 2025 to discuss challenges, enablers, and gains related to data sharing and AI-driven solutions for sustainable food systems. Two breakout room sessions explored perspectives from both consumers/citizens and industry/food system actors on data sharing and AI in food systems.

This practice abstract discusses industry & food system actors' views on key bottlenecks preventing data sharing, particularly data related with health and consumers, supply chain and production, waste and environmental, social and behavioural, animal welfare, and business and management.

- **Commercial and business:** concerns include the commercial sensitivity of data, private interests against sharing, and a general lack of industry transparency. Additionally, companies often see no clear benefit, "win-win" scenario, or value proposition for open data sharing, leading to reluctance or secrecy driven by competitiveness.
- **Trust and fear:** Lack of trust among stakeholders (e.g. industry, consumers) is a relevant concern, linked to fear of data misuse and loss of control once shared. This fear, sometimes coupled with individualism, hinders open and transparent data sharing.
- **Technical and operational challenges:** Bottlenecks include technology and process limitations, such as actors (e.g., farmers) lacking the capacity or suitable tools (with good UI/UX) for efficient data collection and processing. Furthermore, low technological literacy among many actors is a barrier. Finally, small-scale actors may struggle to identify the incentive for data sharing.
- **Privacy and security,** which is related to existing regulations (e.g. GDPR) and other general privacy laws. The unwillingness to collect and share sensitive data due to regulations and potential consequences are also a challenge.

The aforementioned information is available and further detailed in the joint report developed by the #Data4Food Cluster "What Helps and What Hurts When Sharing Data for Sustainable Food Solutions."

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